

KETO-LACTOL TAUTOMERISM. PART VII. SYNTHESIS OF *CYCLO-*HEXANE-1-ACETYL-1-ACETIC ACID, *CYCLO*HEXANE-1-BENZOYL-1-ACETIC ACID AND OTHER RELATED COMPOUNDS AND EXAMINATION OF THEIR BEHAVIOUR

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*cyclo*Hexane-1-acetyl-1-acetic acid has been synthesised. It does not show any tautomeric tendency of either keto-lactol or keto-cyclol type. No tendency for the said tautomerism could be induced by substitution of the acetyl group by either a benzoyl or anisoyl group. *cyclo*Hexane-1-oxalyl-1-acetic acid has been claimed to show tautomerism of the keto-cyclol type. In the light of the above observation a re-examination of this acid become necessary. The acid has been synthesised and put to the known tests but it fails to exhibit any tautomeric tendency.

Although occasional references appear in the literature to the tendency of γ -ketonic acids to show a remarkable capacity for ring chain tautomerism of keto-cyclol type (I) (Deshapande and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1438; Singh and Thorpe, *ibid.*, 1923, 123, 113) and of keto-lactol type (II) (Rothstein and Shoppee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 532); the problem does not appear to have been systematically studied.

The examination of the ketonic acids of the type (III) (Qudrat-i-Khuda, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 201, 713) suggests that valuable information can be gathered from a study of the γ -ketonic acids of the type (IV, where 'X' can be different substituents such as methyl, carboxyl, phenyl or anisoyl group).

With this idea an extensive study of various compounds of the series has been made. Some of these only constitute the subject matter of the present communication.

*cyclo*Hexane-1-acetyl-1-acetic acid (IV, X=COCH₃; R=H) has been prepared from *cyclo*hexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (IV, X=COOH; R=H) by the method of Lapworth and Mc Rae (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2741). The anhydride of this acid through its methyl hydrogen ester gives an acid chloride, which could be converted into methyl *cyclo*hexane-1-acetyl-1-acetate (cf. Rothstein and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2011) with zinc methyl iodide.

The ketonic acid (IV, X=COCH₃; R=H,) is allowed to be acted upon by a concentrated solution of potassium hydroxide but no tautomerism of the keto-cyclol type could be observed here. The acid also remains unaffected by either acetyl chloride or

acetic anhydride, both of which do not yield the acetyl lactol (V, R=Ac; X=CH₃) as they do with ordinary laevulinic acid.

The configuration of the ketonic acid has been settled by its conversion into the semicarbazone. It does not undergo the change into ethoxy ester (V, R=Et; X=Me) on esterification and on Clemmensen reduction the ketonic compound changes into *cyclohexane-1-ethyl-1-acetic acid* (IV, X=Et; R=H).

This lack of tendency of the acid to show the tautomeric capacity, which *cyclohexane-1-oxalyl-1-acetic acid* exhibits to a very remarkable degree (Lanfear and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2865), we are led to believe that the change of methyl group for a negative group may develop the expected capacity. We have synthesised *cyclohexane-1-benzoyl-1-acetic acid* (IV, X=COPh; R=H) from the acid chloride of the acid-ester of (IV, X=COOH; R=H) and benzene by Friedel-Craft's reaction. The configuration of the acid (IV, X=COPh; R=H) has been decided from the fact that it gives the benzylacetic acid (IV, X=CH₂Ph; R=H) on reduction and on hydrolysis it produces a well characterised ketonic acid which gives a semicarbazone without any difficulty.

cyclohexane-1-benzoyl-1-acetic acid also could not be converted into the lactonic compound or into the cyclol structure on being treated with acetic anhydride and potassium hydroxide respectively.

It was thought that perhaps by increasing the negative character of the phenyl residue still further, the tautomeric change in *cyclohexane-1-anisoyl-1-acetic acid* might be induced.

The synthesis of the anisoyl compound (IV, R=CO.C₆H₄.OMe; X=Me) has been very carefully effected. There is no doubt about its being a ketonic compound, as no difficulty is encountered in the formation of its semicarbazone or in its reduction to the anisyl compound (IV, R=CH₂.C₆H₄.OMe; X=H). But this compound also shows no tendency to give a cyclol or a lactol derivative as is expected.

We therefore felt it necessary to repeat the work of Lanfear and Thorpe (*loc cit.*) and to see if the keto-acid (IV, X=CO.CO₂H; R=H) actually exhibited any tendency to its conversion into the cyclol acid (VI) as has been claimed by earlier workers and on which observation the important theory of valency deflexion by substituents has grown up. For the synthesis of the ketonic acid (IV, X=CO.CO₂H; X=H), we selected the method of Bardhan, employed in the synthesis of Balbiano's acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2591, 2604), *cyclohexane-1-acetyl-1-acetic acid* on oxidation with potassium permanganate gives the keto-glutaric acid (IV, X=CO.CO₂H; R=H), m.p. 130°. The identity of this acid with that of Lanfear and Thorpe has been established by its preparation by the method described by them and thereafter their direct comparison.

We are very much surprised to find that even after repeated treatment of the *cyclohexane-1-oxalyl-1-acetic acid* with a concentrated solution of potassium hydroxide, as suggested by Lanfear and Thorpe, the original ketonic acid is recovered, practically quantitatively unchanged. The experiment was repeated.

(VI)

The conclusions regarding keto-cyclol tautomeric change of Thorpe and his collaborators must therefore be accepted with some reserve. It is expected that further work in this direction will give us more definite idea about the valency deflection hypothesis in its application to keto-cyclol tautomeric change.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetate was prepared by boiling the anhydride of *cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* (46 g.) with methyl alcohol (28 c.c.) for 5 hours under a reflux. The half ester was isolated in the usual way after removing the excess of methyl alcohol as completely as possible. The heavy oil that was then isolated was left in a vacuum desiccator for about 48 hours, when it set to a solid crystalline mass. A portion of it was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-50°) when it melted at 57°. (Found: C, 59.89; H, 7.88. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0 per cent).

Methyl cyclohexane-1-acetyl-1-acetate.—For the preparation of this compound, the half ester of *cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* (20 g.) was warmed with thionyl chloride (13 c.c.) at 45-48° for 1½ hours. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed at 50° under reduced pressure. The acid chloride thus obtained was diluted with anhydrous benzene (25 c.c.) and added to a cooled solution of zinc methyl iodide, prepared from methyl iodide (20.8 c.c.), ethyl acetate (10.8 c.c.), sodium-dried benzene (25 c.c.) and zinc-copper couple (43 g.). The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way when methyl keto-ester was obtained as a mobile liquid with a characteristic smell boiling at 122°/8 mm., yield 14 g. On redistillation it boiled at 120°/7 mm. (Found: C, 66.54; H, 8.78. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 66.66; H, 9.04 per cent). The keto-ester gave a *semicarbazone* very readily when crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m.p. 148°. (Found: C, 56.78; H, 7.99. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_5\text{N}_3$ requires C, 56.47; H, 8.23 per cent).

Ethyl cyclohexane-1-acetyl-1-acetate was prepared precisely in the same way as the methyl ester, only with this difference that ethyl *cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetate* was a liquid. The keto-ester boiled at 137-138°/7mm. Rothstein and Thorpe (*loc. cit.*) gave a *semicarbazone*, m.p. 111°. (Found: C, 58.12; H, 8.12. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_5\text{N}_3$ requires C, 57.99; H, 8.54 per cent).

cyclohexane-1-acetyl-1-acetic acid was prepared from the methyl ester (20 g.), potassium hydroxide (20 g.) in water (20 c.c.) and rectified spirit (250 c.c.). The

acid was isolated in the usual way as a crystalline solid from benzene and light petroleum, m. p. 82° (cf. Rothstein and Thorpe, *loc. cit.*). [Found : M. W. (titration), 184.2. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires M. W., 184].

The acid was esterified by Phelps and Tillotson's method when it gave the normal ethyl ester, just described, giving the same semicarbazone, m. p. 111°

The above acid (1 g.) was mixed with acetyl chloride (10 c. c.) and refluxed on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, excess of acetyl chloride was distilled off and the residue was treated with water and sodium carbonate solution when 0.8 g. of the original acid was recovered unchanged. When acetic anhydride was substituted for acetyl chloride and the mixture was heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the original acid was recovered unchanged. The acid (2 g.) on being boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid underwent no change; 1.8 g. were recovered. When 2 g. of the acid were heated with 64 g. of potassium hydroxide in 36 c. c. of water for 3 hours, 1.8 g. of the acid were isolated unchanged from the mixture. All these experiments show that the acid has no capacity to undergo a tautomeric change.

1-Ethyl cyclohexane-1-acetic acid was obtained by the reduction of cyclohexane-1-acetyl-1-acetic acid (3 g.), mixed with amalgamated zinc (15 g.) prepared by leaving it in contact with a solution of mercuric chloride (25 g.) in water (100 c. c.) for 1 hour. The mixture of the acid and zinc was heated under reflux with concentrated hydrochloric acid (15 c. c.) for 17 hours. The solution was then cooled well and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with a solution of sodium carbonate and the alkaline washing on acidification precipitated the acid, which was purified in the usual way when 1.5 g. of it were obtained. It crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum, m. p. 123°. [Found : C, 70.39; H, 10.48; M., W. (by titration), 170.4. $C_{11}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 70.58; H, 10.58 per cent. M. W., 170].

Methyl cyclohexane-1-benzoyl-1-acetate was prepared by converting the methyl cyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetate (15 g.) into the acid chloride by heating it with thionyl chloride (10 c. c.) at 45-48° for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. Excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off under reduced pressure at about 50° and the acid chloride was mixed up with benzene (35 c. c.), dried over sodium. This mixture was efficiently cooled and finely powdered aluminium chloride (16.5 g.) was added in small quantities at a time. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight and the next day it was heated at 65-70° for about 3 hours. This was then decomposed with ice and dilute hydrochloric acid. Excess of benzene was then expelled by distillation in a current of steam and the residual heavy oil was extracted with ether. This was purified in the usual way when it solidified to a crystalline mass, yield 12.5 g. It was recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 64°. (Found : C, 73.04; H, 7.48. $C_{16}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 73.84; H, 7.69 per cent). This keto-ester did not readily give a semicarbazone but on being refluxed on the water-bath for several hours with semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate in methyl alcoholic solution and on being left over for about 12 hours, a semicarbazone was isolated, which crystallised from aqueous methyl alcohol, m. p. 155°. (Found : C, 64.61; H, 7.22. $C_{17}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires C, 64.35; H, 7.25 per cent).

cycloHexane-1-benzoyl-1-acetic acid was obtained by mixing the ester (7.5 g.) and

potassium hydroxide (7.5 g.) in water (7.5 c.c.) together and diluting the same with 200 c. c. of rectified spirit when a clear solution was obtained. The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 7 hours. Excess of alcohol was then distilled off and the residue was diluted with water (70 c. c.). This was extracted with ether and the alkaline solution was then acidified with hydrochloric acid and the solution was saturated with ammonium sulphate. The acid was then extracted with ether and isolated as usual. The oily residue solidified, yield 6.5 g. It crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m. p. 118°. [Found : C, 73.17; H, 7.26; M. W. (by titration), 246.3. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 73.13; H, 7.31 per cent. M.W., 246] It gave a *semicarbazone*, m. p. 133°. (Found : C, 63.54; H, 6.52. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires C, 63.36; H, 6.93 per cent). The acid showed no tendency to tautomerise under the ordinary conditions.

The acid (3 g.) was heated with amalgamated zinc (15 g.) and hydrochloric acid (15 c. c.) for 22 hours. The product was isolated as usual when it separated as a heavy oil, which solidified in a vacuum desiccator. *cycloHexane-1-benzyl-1-acetic acid* crystallises from acetic acid, m.p. 92°. [Found : C, 77.67; H, 8.43; M. W. (by titration), 232. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 77.58; H, 8.62 per cent. M. W., 232].

Methyl cyclohexane-1-anisoyl-1-acetate was prepared from the acid chloride of methyl *cyclohexane-1-acetate-1-acetic acid* (25 g.) which reacted with anisole (16 g.) in dry carbon disulphide (100 c.c.) in presence of finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (30 g.). The temperature was kept low for over 18 hours and then it was heated to about 65-70° for 2 hours. This was then cooled and decomposed with crushed ice and hydrochloric acid. Excess of anisole and carbon disulphide were removed in a current of steam and the residue was extracted with ether. The residue on purification gave a solid (20 g.) which crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 86°. (Found : C, 70.21; H, 7.5. $C_{17}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 70.34; H, 7.58 per cent).

This ester (15 g.) was hydrolysed with potassium hydroxide (15 g.) in 15 c.c. of water and 200 c.c. of spirit by heating for 8 hours. The alcohol was then removed under reduced pressure and the solution diluted and extracted with ether. The alkaline solution on acidification precipitated heavy oil which when purified solidified and crystallised from dilute acetic acid. This acid, *cyclohexane-1-anisoyl-1-acetic acid* melts at 126-27°. [Found : C, 69.61; H, 7.22; M. W. (by titration), 276.4. $C_{16}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 69.56; H, 7.24 per cent. M. W., 276]. The acid remains unaffected by the usual reagents for lactol or cyclol formation. The acid (10 g.) was reduced by 60 g. of amalgamated zinc and hydrochloric acid (40 c.c.) in course of 25 hours. *cycloHexane-1-p-methoxybenzoyl-1-acetic acid* was obtained as a crystalline solid, which crystallised from dilute alcohol and melted at 81-82°. [Found : C, 73.32; H, 8.4; M. W. (by titration), 262.2. $C_{16}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 73.28; H, 8.39 per cent M. W., 262].

cycloHexane-1-ozalyl-1-acetic Acid.—To a mixture of *cyclohexane-1-acetyl-1-acetic acid* (6.1 g.), potassium hydroxide (2 g.) and water (200 c.c.) was added a solution of potassium permanganate (12 g.) and potassium hydroxide (4 g.) in water (300 c.c.). The mixture was kept in ice-cold water for several hours and then at the ordinary temperature for 3 days, when it assumed a greenish tinge. This colour was discharged

with a few c.c. of rectified spirit and precipitated manganese dioxide was filtered off and extracted several times with hot water and then combined aqueous filtrate was concentrated, cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid and it was extracted several times with ether. The ethereal layer on drying and removal of the solvent gave a crystalline solid mass (4.8 g.) This was crystallised several times from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum, m. p. 130°. [Found : C, 56.10 ; H, 6.44 ; M. W. (by titration), 214.4. $C_{10}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 56.04 ; H, 6.49 per cent. M. W., 214]. The acid gave a quinoxaline derivative which crystallised from methyl alcohol, m. p. 246°. (Found : C, 67.22 ; H, 6.18 ; N, 9.92. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_2$ requires C, 67.13 ; H, 6.29 ; N, 9.79 per cent). (Lanfear and Thorpe, *loc. cit.*).

This keto-acid on reduction yielded *cyclohexane-1:1-diacetic acid* which was found to be identical with the acid prepared otherwise.

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